

Synthesis and Biological Screening of N^4 -Phthalimidomethyl Sulphonamides

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The N -substituted-phthalimides are known to possess various medicinal and biological properties¹. N -Morpholinomethylphthalimide and N -diethylaminomethylphthalimide are found to possess local anaesthetic property². Earlier report³ shows that when carbonyl group from phthalimide is substituted by thiocarbonyl group and hydrogens attached to nitrogen in phthalimide is substituted by trihalomethyl group, the resulting compound exhibits significant antibacterial property. Considering the utility of substituted-phthalimides, we have synthesised phthalimidomethylsulphonamides, to see how far the N -substituted-phthalimides show antibacterial activity as compared to the sulphonamides⁴.

Results and Discussion

N^4 -Phthalimidomethyl sulphonamides were synthesised by Mannich reaction of phthalimide, sulphonamide and 37% formaldehyde solution in ethanol. They showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The uv-spectral data showed a slight bathochromic shift in λ_{\max} of the Mannich bases (in dioxane) as compared to that of p -aminobenzene sulphonamide (in ethanol) (vide Experimental), possibly due to substitution at N^4 -nitrogen of sulphonamide molecule by phthalimidomethyl group. This is in agreement with earlier reports⁵, when it was found that N^4 -acetylaminosulphanilamide gave λ_{\max} at 264 nm as compared to 260 nm of the sulphanilamide. The Mannich bases showed characteristic ir bands at 3420 ± 20 (anilino of sulphanilamide moiety), 3360 and 3080 (SO_2NH), 2925 ± 5 (CH_2 stretch and bend), 1775 ± 15 and 1715 ± 15 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ of phthalimide moiety).

Antimicrobial screening: The Mannich bases were studied for their antibacterial property using filter paper disc technique⁶ at concentration of 20 mg ml^{-1} , against various Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, viz. *B. anthracis*, *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, *P. aeruginosa*, *C. pyogenes* and *S. aureus*.

The results (Table 1) show that overall antibacterial activities (zone of inhibition 14–28 mm) of N^4 -phthalimidomethyl derivatives of sulphanilamide, sulphadiazene, sulphamerazine, sulphathiazole and sulphaphenazole are slightly higher than their parent sulphonamides against all the organisms. Mannich bases of phthalimides with sulphasomidine and sulphadimidine show comparable ac-

tivity (16–26 mm) with that of the respective parent sulphonamides. Mannich base of sulphamethoxazole also show same order of activity (20–26 mm) as the parent sulphonamide (24–28 mm), but is less active (22–24 mm) against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* as compared to the parent sulphonamide (26–28 mm). In the preliminary screening, the N^4 -phthalimidomethylsulphathiazole and N^4 -phthalimidomethylsulphamethoxazole in oral LD_{50} dose of 1500 mg/kg of the body weight did not show any adverse toxic effects.

Experimental

A 37% formaldehyde solution (0.0125 mol) was added to an ice-cooled mixture of phthalimide (0.01 mol) and sulphonamide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) with stirring. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 3.5–4.0 with HCl. It was then kept at room temperature for 0.5 h and refluxed on a water-bath for ~3 h followed by removal of ethanol by distillation. The resulting solution on keeping at ice-temperature for 4–5 days afforded N^4 -phthalimidomethylsulphonamide. The crude product was crystallised

NOTE

from DMF to yield 1-8 (40-66%) : 1, m.p. 184°, λ_{\max} 266 nm (parent sulphonamide, sulphanilamide 260 nm); 2, 186°, λ_{\max} 241, 270 (sulphadiazine 241 nm); 3, 224°, λ_{\max} 292, 301 (sulphamerazine 260 nm); 4, 157°, λ_{\max} 268 (sulphadimidine 260, 300 nm); 5, 180°, λ_{\max} 243, 279 (sulphasomidine 241, 260 nm); 6, 154°, λ_{\max} 260 nm; 7, 212-13°, λ_{\max} 263, 289 (sulphathiazole 260, 283 nm); 8, 179°, λ_{\max} 241, 280 nm. M.ps. are uncorrected.

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